

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

PRIMARY CRACKS IN ATOMICALLY SMOOTH CRYSTALS ALKALINE EARTH ELEMENTS

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Abstract

An alkaline earth metal crystal consists of a surface layer of size $R(I)$, which we will call the σ_1 phase, and a base material, which we will call the σ_2 phase. Since the surface energy of the layer $R(I)$ with σ_1 is 3 times less than the surface energy of the bulk phase, the destruction of the metal starts from the surface layer. For crystals with identical atoms, the share of space occupied by them in one cube is 68-74% for alkaline earth metal. The rest (26-32%) is occupied by empty space. After relaxation, we will call this space the maximum field of primary cracks. For us, the most important thing is the fact that the length of this crack L is equal to the thickness of the surface layer of the alkaline earth metal $R(I)$. This crack length reflects the peculiarity that it is associated not only with the geometry of crystal lattices, but also with the physical properties of crystals. We have proposed a model for calculating the length of primary cracks that appear in metals due to the presence of a surface layer $R(I)$. Griffiths considered the change in the energy of a body with a crack under loading and obtained an energy criterion for failure. Our calculation of the crack length L for an alkaline earth metal gave $L = 2.52 \cdot 10^{-9}$ m, which is very acceptable for our model.

Keywords: surface layer, crack, alkali metal, energy, model, surface, crystal, destruction.

Introduction

Alkaline earth metals (AEM) are chemical elements of the 2nd group of the periodic table: beryllium (Be), magnesium (Mg), calcium (Ca), strontium (Sr), barium (Ba), radium (Ra) [1]. Only calcium, strontium, barium and radium are often referred to as alkaline

earth metals. With rare exceptions, beryllium and magnesium. But according to the nomenclature of work [2], all elements of the 2nd group are referred to the AEM. Beryllium and magnesium are closer to aluminum in their chemical properties. We will consider all AEMs, the physical properties that we will use in the calculations are presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Physical properties of alkaline earth metals.

Element/property	Be	Mg	Ca	Sr	Ba	Ra
M (g/mol) - mass	9.0122	24.304	40.078	87.621	137.327	226.025
ρ (g/cm ³) - density	1.848	1.738	1.55	2.54	3.50	5.50
Structure	P6/mmm	P6/mmm	Fm3m	Fm3m	Im3m	Im3m
Lattice parameters (nm)	a = 0.2286 c = 0.3584	a = 0.3203 c = 0.5200	0.5580	0.6080	0.5020	0.5148
T_m (K) - melting point	1551	923	1112	1042	1002	1233
E (GPa) - Young's modulus	287	45	20	15.7	13	-
G (GPa) - shear modulus	132	17	7.4	6.03	4.9	-
K - bulk modulus of elasticity (GPa)	130	35	17	-	9.6	-

AEM crystals and their structure are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. - AEM crystals and their structure.

In [3, 4], we proposed a model for determining the thickness of the surface layer of atomically smooth crystals of many elements. She looks like this:

$$R(I) = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \nu \cdot (m) \quad (1)$$

Equation (1) shows that the thickness of the surface layer $R(I)$ is determined by one fundamental parameter, the molar (atomic) volume of the element ($\nu = M/\rho$, M is the molar mass, ρ is the density). The experimental determination of $R(I)$ for atomically smooth

crystals is described in [5, 6] (for example, for silicon, this layer depth is $R(I) = 3.2$ nm, and for gold, $R(I) = 1.2$ nm). From where it can be seen that the $R(I)$ layer for most chemical elements is a nanostructure. Since AEM crystals have the structure of hexagonal close packing (hcp) in the case of Be and Mg, face-centered cubic (fcc) in the case of Ca and Sr, body-centered cubic (bcc) in the case of Ba and Ra (Fig. 1), equation (1) is transformed to the form [7]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 R(I) &= 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \cdot M/\rho, (m) \\
 R(I)_{x=a} &= 0,54 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot x(a)^3, (m) \\
 R(I)_{y=b} &= 0,54 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot y(b)^3, (m)
 \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

$$R(I)_{z=c} = 0,54 \cdot 10^{-11} \cdot z(c)^3, (m)$$

The values of the $R(I)$ layer for AEM are given in Table 2, while using the following relations [8]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 Pm3m, Z = 1, l_{100} = 2R(I), l_{110} = R(I)\sqrt{2}, l_{111} = 2R(I)/\sqrt{3} \\
 Im3m, Z = 2, l_{100} = R(I), l_{110} = R(I)\sqrt{2}, l_{111} = R(I)/\sqrt{3} \\
 Fm3m, Z = 4, l_{100} = R(I), l_{110} = R(I)/\sqrt{2}, l_{111} = 2R(I)/\sqrt{3} \\
 Fd3m, Z = 8, l_{100} = R(I)/2, l_{110} = R(I)/\sqrt{2}, l_{111} = 2R(I)/\sqrt{3}
 \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

To calculate the free energy of the bulk sample $\sigma(hkl)$ and the layer $R(I)$, the following formulas should be used [7, 9]:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma(hkl) &= 0,7 \cdot 10^{-3} \cdot T_m, J/m^2 \\
 \sigma_a &= 10^{-3} \cdot T_m \cdot R_a(I)/R(I), J/m^2 \\
 \sigma_b &= 10^{-3} \cdot T_m \cdot R_b(I)/R(I), J/m^2 \\
 \sigma_c &= 10^{-3} \cdot T_m \cdot R_c(I)/R(I), J/m^2
 \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

To calculate σ_1 using formula (4) for the R(I) layer, it is necessary to take into account the size dependence of the melting temperature using the [7]:

$$T_m(h) = T_m(K) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{R(I)}{h}\right), \quad h \gg R(I) \quad (5)$$

$$T_m(h) = T_m(K) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{R(I)}{R(I) + h}\right), \quad 0 \leq h \leq R(I).$$

where $T_m(K)$ is the melting temperature of the bulk sample, h is the layer coordinate.

In this article, the concept of atomically smooth crystals is presented and the length of primary cracks in AEM is presented for the first time.

Atomically smooth surfaces of AEM

Figure 2. - Methods for preparing atomically smooth surfaces (a); types of faces of cubic crystals according to Frank and Cabrera (b) [5, 6].

If the surface plane is electrically neutral, then surface relaxation is observed (Fig. 3a). If the surface plane of atoms has complete order (the polar plane), then the reconstruction of the surface in the transverse direction is observed, the reason for which is the desire to neutralize the excess surface charge (Fig. 3b). Most metals are characterized by relaxation.

Both of these processes lead to the formation of an anisotropic layer R(I), which we will call the σ_1 phase, and a ground substance, which we will call the σ_2 phase (Fig. 4a). The layer thickness R(I) is calculated using formulas (1) and (2), and the work of separating the phases σ_1 and σ_2 , called the work of adhesion, is given by the Dupré expression [10] (Fig. 4b):

$$W_a = \sigma_1 + \sigma_2 - \sigma_{12} \approx \sigma_1 + \sigma_2, \quad (\text{J/m}^2) \quad (6)$$

The adhesion energy is of interest to the calculation of the internal stresses of AEM, which arise due to the presence of uncompensated atoms on the surface and in the volume and the formation of a surface layer of size R(I). Internal stresses ε_{is} between phases σ_1 and σ_2 can be calculated using the formula [10]:

$$\varepsilon_{is} = \sqrt{[W_a / R(I)] \cdot E}. \quad (\text{Pa}) \quad (7)$$

where σ_{12} is the surface energy at the phase boundary, which is negligible due to the second order phase transition.

Figure 3. - Schematic illustration of normal (left) and lateral (right) relaxations of the upper atomic layer (a); surface reconstruction $(1 \times 1) \rightarrow (2 \times 1)$ (b).

Figure 4. - Phases of AEM crystals (a) and work of adhesion (b).

The adhesion force for AEM is equal to:

$$F_1 = \sigma_1 \cdot R(I). \tag{8}$$

Calculation data according to formulas (1) - (8) are given in Table. 2. Here, in brackets, the values $n = R(I)/a$ (a is the lattice constant) of monolayers of AEM crystals are given. Data on the work of adhesion are shown in table. 3.

Table 2.

Surface layer thickness R(I), adhesion force F₁, values of internal stresses ε_{is}.

Metal	(hkl)	R(I), nm	F ₁ , nN	ε _{is} , MPa
Be	a = b	0.66 (3)	0.25	25500
	c	2.52 (7)	3.69	25500
Mg	a = b	1.77 (6)	0.36	4740
	c	7.59 (15)	6.65	4740
Ca	(100)	2.38 (4)	0.55	2915
	(110)	1.70 (3)	0.28	2915
	(111)	2.80 (5)	0.77	2915
Sr	(100)	5.86 (9)	1.23	1594
	(110)	4.19 (7)	0.65	1594
	(111)	6.89 (11)	1.77	1594
Ba	(100)	6.67 (11)	1.40	1334
	(110)	9.34 (18)	2.60	1334
	(111)	3.92 (7)	0.49	1334
Ra	(100)	6.99 (13)	1.81	-
	(110)	9.78 (19)	3.49	-
	(111)	4.11 (8)	0.62	-

Table 3.

Adhesion energy W_a of AEM.

Metal	(hkl)	σ ₁ , J/m ²	σ ₂ , J/m ²	W _a , J/m ²
Be	a = b	0.384	1.280	1.664
	c	1.466	4.886	6.352
Mg	a = b	0.204	0.681	0.885
	c	0.876	2.919	3.795
Ca	(100)	0.233	0.778	1.011
	(110)	0.167	0.556	0.723
	(111)	0.275	0.915	1.190
Sr	(100)	0.219	0.729	0.948
	(110)	0.156	0.521	0.677
	(111)	0.257	0.858	1.115
Ba	(100)	0.210	0.701	0.911
	(110)	0.278	0.982	1.206
	(111)	0.124	0.412	0.536
Ra	(100)	0.259	0.863	1.122
	(110)	0.362	1.208	1.570
	(111)	0.152	0.508	0.660

From Table 2 shows the anisotropy of the layer thickness R(I) for hcp, fcc, and bcc crystals (Fig. 1). For hcp beryllium and magnesium R(I) in the a = b plane, the R(I) layer increases from 0.66 to 1.77 nm, and the number of monolayers increases from 3 to 6. This occurs with an increase in the atomic number from 4 for Be to 12 for Mg. In the c plane, the R(I) layer increases from 2.52 to 7.59 nm, and the number of monolayers increases from 7 to 15. For fcc calcium and strontium, the R(I) layer increases from 2.38 to 5.86 nm in the (100) plane, from 1.70 to 4.19 nm in the (110) plane and from 2.80 to 6.89 nm in the (111) plane, and the number of monolayers from 4 to 9 in the (100) plane. The maximum dimensions of the R(I) layer are observed in the (111) plane. For bcc barium and radium, the R(I) layer increases from 6.67 to 6.99 nm in the (100) plane, from 9.34 to 9.78 nm in the (110) plane, and from 3.92 to 4.11 nm in the (111) plane. The maximum dimensions of the R(I) layer are observed in the (110) plane. Tab. 2 shows that the layer thickness R(I) is an anisotropic nanostructure for hcp, fcc, and bcc

crystals. The value of internal stresses ε_{is}, on the contrary, does not exhibit anisotropy for all planes of these crystals. This is due to the fact that when calculating the value of ε_{is} using formula (7), we did not take into account the anisotropy of the Young's modulus E, taken from Table. 1. The value of internal stresses ε_{is} decreases from 25500 MPa for Be to 1334 MPa for Ba, i.e. almost 20 times.

The adhesion force F₁ (the force of intermolecular interaction) for Be is 0.25 10⁻⁹ N in the a = b plane and 3.69 10⁻⁹ N; for Ca, 0.55 10⁻⁹ N in the (100) plane, 0.28 10⁻⁹ N in the (110) plane, and 0.77 10⁻⁹ N in the (111) plane. For comparison: the force of attraction between an electron and a proton in a hydrogen atom is F = 0.2 10⁻⁹ N; sound pressure strength in the human ear at the threshold of hearing - F = 2 10⁻⁹ N; locomotive traction force F = 6 10⁵ N; force of attraction between the Earth and the Moon F = 2 10²⁰ N.

Model of primary cracks in AEM crystals

For crystals with identical atoms, the share of space occupied by them in one cube is 74 % for Be, Mg, Ca and Sr metals, and 68 % for Ba and Ra metals. The

rest (26 and 32 %) is occupied by empty space. After reconstruction and relaxation, we will call this space the maximum field of primary cracks. For us, the most important thing is the fact that the length of this crack L is equal to the thickness of the surface layer $R(I)$ of AEM. This crack length reflects the peculiarity that it is associated not only with the geometry of crystal lattices, but also with the physical properties of crystals, namely:

with the type of chemical bond (ionic, covalent, metallic, etc.); porosity, anisotropy and other properties.

It was shown above that the crack length L is equal to the thickness of the AEM surface layer $R(I)$, the value of which is determined in [6]:

$$L = 0,17 \cdot 10^{-9} \nu \cdot (m) \quad (9)$$

Table 4.

Crack length, pore size, specific surface area of AEM				
Metal	(hkl)	L, nm	r, nm	S_{sp} , m ² /g
Be	a = b	0.66	0.10	4.92
	c	2.52	0.39	1.29
Mg	a = b	1.77	0.27	1.95
	c	7.59	1.17	0.45
Ca	(100)	2.38	0.37	1.63
	(110)	1.70	0.26	2.28
	(111)	2.80	0.43	1.38
Sr	(100)	5.86	0.90	0.40
	(110)	4.19	0.64	0.56
	(111)	6.89	1.06	0.34
Ba	(100)	6.67	1.03	0.26
	(110)	9.34	1.44	0.18
	(111)	3.92	0.60	0.44
Ra	(100)	6.99	1.08	0.156
	(110)	9.78	1.51	0.112
	(111)	4.11	0.63	0.265

Theoretically, in a layer consisting of one-dimensional spherical particles, the average pore size will be equal to the size of the empty space formed with a single-layer staggered arrangement of three spheres. The pore radius, in this case, is equal to:

$$r = 0.154 \cdot L \cdot (m) \quad (10)$$

When the particles are in the form of spheres of the same diameter L , the specific surface area S_{sp} is given by:

$$S_{sp} = 6 / \rho \cdot L \cdot (m^2/g) \quad (11)$$

Parameters (9) - (11) will be presented in Table 4.

According to the IUPAC definition, porous bodies are divided into microporous (pore diameter less than 2 nm), mesoporous (from 2 to 50 nm), and macroporous (more than 50 nm) [11]. In our case (Table 4), we have microporous AEMs. In materials subjected to deformation, it is customary to distinguish the following mechanisms of pore formation [12]:

- due to the merging of dislocation cracks, which are formed during the deceleration of slip planes;
- due to the formation of steps on the grain boundaries at the exit point of the sliding planes with subsequent sliding along the boundary;
- due to coagulation of vacancies;
- due to the annihilation of dislocations in opposite planes of the cluster, spaced from each other by 5-7 Burgers vectors.

A common mechanism for the formation of pores is through the formation of local accumulations of vacancies with their subsequent condensation into pores. Therefore, the pore can be considered as a complex of vacancies. The length of a microcrack (Table 4) is formed due to the formation of dislocations. The mechanism of dislocation formation is one of the least studied issues in the theory of crystal lattice imperfections [12]. After reconstruction and relaxation of AEM, edge and screw dislocations can appear (Fig. 5).

Figure 5. - Edge (a), screw (b) and mixed (c) dislocations [12].

Griffiths [13] considered the change in the energy of a body with a crack under loading and obtained an energy fracture criterion, according to which a crack acquires the ability to spontaneously propagate only when the rate of release of elastic energy during growth becomes equal to or exceeds the energy of the newly formed surface:

$$\Delta W = \frac{\sigma_{\varepsilon\delta}^2 \pi L^2}{2E} + 2\sigma L \quad (12)$$

- total energy change for the case of a plane stress state, where σ - specific surface energy, E - Young's modulus, σ_{cr} - applied stress, L - crack size, ν - Poisson's ratio.

The value of critical stresses at which a crack is capable of unstable growth can be found from the conditions:

$$\frac{\partial W}{\partial L} = 0, \quad \frac{\sigma_{\varepsilon\delta}^2 \pi L}{E} = 2\sigma. \quad (13)$$

Let us calculate the crack length L for hcp beryllium Be from formula (13) using the data in Table 1. 1 - 4, with $\sigma = \sigma_1 + \sigma_2$ and $\sigma_{cr} = \varepsilon_{is}$. We have: $L(a = b) = 955 \cdot 10^9 / 2041 \cdot 10^{18} = 0.47 \cdot 10^{-9}$ m; $L(s) = 1.79 \cdot 10^{-9}$ m. From the table. 4 we have: $L(a = b) = 0.66 \cdot 10^{-9}$ m and $L(c) = 2.52 \cdot 10^{-9}$ m, which is very acceptable for our model. For fcc calcium Ca we have: $L(100) = 1.57 \cdot 10^{-9}$, $L(110) = 1.14 \cdot 10^{-9}$, $L(111) = 1.87 \cdot 10^{-9}$. From Table. 4 we have: $L(100) = 2.38 \cdot 10^{-9}$, $L(110) = 1.70 \cdot 10^{-9}$, $L(111) = 2.80 \cdot 10^{-9}$, which is also very close to our model within experimental errors. For bcc barium Ba we have: $L(100) = 4.24 \cdot 10^{-9}$, $L(110) = 5.61 \cdot 10^{-9}$, $L(111) = 2.49 \cdot 10^{-9}$. From Table. 4 we have: $L(100) = 6.67 \cdot 10^{-9}$, $L(110) = 9.34 \cdot 10^{-9}$, $L(111) = 3.92 \cdot 10^{-9}$, which is also very close to our model within experimental errors. This implies the conclusion that the Griffith theory [13] should be subject to errors related to the length of the microcrack L (formulas 1-9). A number of microcrack formation models noted in [12-14]: the Zener-Straw-Petch model, the Cottrell model, the Ballaf-Gilman model, the Orvan-Straw model, the Koble model, the Nabarro-Herring model, complicate the Griffiths model, but do not determine the length microcracks, as it is done in our work presented.

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Conclusion

At present, three micromechanisms of destruction of metals are distinguished [14]: ductile fracture, transcrystalline and intergranular cleavage. In addition,

there are failure micromechanisms associated with fatigue, creep, and dynamic loading. However, the primary reason for the formation of microcracks, even for atomically smooth crystals, is the stresses associated with the formation of a surface nanostructured layer of metals due to the processes of relaxation or surface reconstruction. The calculation of the length of microcracks presented in this paper speaks unambiguously about the applicability of the Griffith theory for describing the fracture of metals.

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